

Orthohydroxyketones and Orthohydroxyketoximes as Indicators for the Direct CyDTA Titration of Ferric Ions

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MARPLE¹ showed the superior accuracy of cyDTA compared to the direct EDTA titration of iron. According to him the end point with chrome Azurol S is much more easily determined than that with thiocyanate or sulphosalicylic acid. It is to be noted however that miligram-amounts of aluminium react with chrome Azurol S to give a violet colour

The optimum pH is 1.0–2.0. 2 drops of 1% indicator solution give satisfactory results. The titrations can be carried out in the temperature range 15°–50°C.

Effect of foreign ions: The titration of synthetic solutions were carried out at pH 1.0. At 1.4 mg concentration of iron, 100 times excess of Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Cl⁻, Br⁻, ClO₄⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, 50 times excess of UO₂²⁺, 20 times excess of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, 10 times excess of Ag⁺, Pb²⁺, Al³⁺, 5 times excess of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, and an equal amount of Cu²⁺ could be tolerated. Mn²⁺, Th⁴⁺, Zr⁴⁺ anions forming stable complex with iron such as phosphates, vanadates, molybdates and tungstates interfered at all levels.

Synthetic solutions containing more than one foreign ions were also analysed with the help of these indicators at pH 1.0. Results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC SOLUTIONS

Metals present	Found Fe ³⁺ mg			
	Orthohydroxy acetophenone	Orthohydroxy propiophenone	Orthohydroxy acetophenone oxime	Orthohydroxy propiophenone oxime
1. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +1.50 mg Na ⁺ +10 mg Ag ⁺	2.80	2.80	2.80	2.80
2. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +25 mg Pd ²⁺ +50 mg K ⁺	2.80	2.80	2.80	2.80
3. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +20 mg Ca ²⁺ +20 mg Sr ²⁺	2.80	2.79	2.80	2.80
4. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +20 mg Sr ²⁺ +20 mg Ba ²⁺	2.81	2.80	2.80	2.81
5. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +20 mg Fe ²⁺ +20 mg Al ³⁺	2.79	2.80	2.81	2.80
6. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +1 mg Cu ²⁺ +10 mg Ni ²⁺	2.80	2.80	2.79	2.80
7. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +10 mg Co ²⁺ +10 mg Ni ²⁺	2.80	2.80	2.80	2.80

which obscures the endpoint for the iron titration. The conditions for the use of thiocyanate indicator are very restrictive. According to Martinez² with sulphosalicylic acid and iron results are high upto 4%. The present paper reports the use of *o*-hydroxy acetophenone, orthohydroxy propiophenone, *o*-hydroxy acetophenone oxime and orthohydroxy-propiophenone oxime as indicators for the direct titration of iron using CyDTA.

Experimental

CyDTA solution: A stock solution of 0.01M CyDTA was prepared by dissolving 3.4 g of CyDTA and 1.6 g sodium hydroxide in 1 lt of distilled water.

Observations: Orthohydroxy acetophenone, orthohydroxy propiophenone, orthohydroxybutyrophenone, orthohydroxyacetophenone oxime, orthohydroxypropiophenone oxime and orthohydroxybutyrophenone oxime give violet colours with ferric ions. Preliminary studies indicated that orthohydroxy butyrophenone and its oxime are not satisfactory indicators; hence the remaining compounds were investigated in detail.

The end point is marked by a sharp colour change from purple to deep yellow on titration with CyDTA.

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Gravimetric and Volumetric Determination of Cd, Zn and Pd as Isoquinoline Halide Complexes and the Simultaneous Determination of Cd-Cu, Cd-Co, Cd-Ni, Zn-Ni, Zn-Cu and Zn-Co

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CADMIUM and zinc were detected as pyridine bromide and pyridine iodide complexes¹. Though this reaction is quite specific for these metals, yet no attempt has been made so far for their determination based upon these reactions. These metals

have also been found to form similar complexes with isoquinoline in the presence of these ions and the form of the precipitate is much better than pyridine but the method has been found to be reproducible only with bromide ions². Palladium also forms a similar complex when its aqueous solution was treated with isoquinoline and iodide ions².

The gravimetric determination is based upon the precipitation of these metals in the presence of isoquinoline solution and halide ions under suitable conditions and weighing the metals as $M(C_9H_7N)_2(X)_2$ while in the volumetric the metal is treated with isoquinoline solution in the presence of a known excess of halide ions, the halide ions were determined mercurimetrically using diphenyl carbazone as the internal indicator. The decrease in the concentration of halide ions corresponded to the metal present.

Since bromide ions only form complexes with cadmium and zinc while thiocyanate forms complexes with Cu, Ni and Co in addition to Cd and Zn³, thus performing two titrations, one in the presence of bromide ions and the second in the presence of thiocyanate ions, the analyses of Cd-Co, Cd-Cu, Cd-Ni, Zn-Ni, Zn-Co and Zn-Cu have been made quite successfully.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions: Solutions of metal nitrate, potassium thiocyanate, potassium bromide and potassium iodide were prepared from B.D.H. (A.R) samples and standardised by known methods⁴. Mercuric nitrate solution was prepared from E. Merck's sample and standardised with potassium thiocyanate solution using diphenyl carbazone as the internal indicator⁴. Freshly prepared alcoholic solution of the indicator was used in all the cases. 6.45 g of isoquinoline was dissolved from freshly distilled sample in 3-4 ml of 85% formic acid and the volume made 100 ml of 0.1M sodium hydroxide and 10% of formic acid was used for adjusting the pH of the solutions. Marconi pH meter was used for the purpose.

Preliminary experiments indicated that the amount of isoquinoline in case of cadmium and zinc should not be less than twice the amount calculated from the equation

where $M = Zn, Cd$ or Pd and $X = Br$ or I , while in case of palladium the amount should not exceed more than twice the amount calculated from the above equation. The optimum pH for cadmium and zinc 4.5-5.5 above 5.5 the precipitate of zinc was completely dissolved while below 4.0 the precipitate of both the metals did not appear. In case of palladium the results were found to be satisfactory in the pH range of 1.5-4.5.

Gravimetric determination of cadmium, zinc and palladium: To the metal solution taken in a 250 ml beaker, added isoquinoline solution and 20-30 ml of 0.2M potassium bromide in case of cadmium and zinc and 20 ml of 0.1M potassium iodide was added in case of palladium. The proper pH were maintained and the solution was allowed to stand for 10-15 min on water bath (60°-70°C) and filtered over G-4 sintered glass crucible. The precipitate was washed once with 3-5 ml of solution prepared (0.5 g of KBr, 1-2 ml of isoquinoline solution, 10-15 ml of ethanol and the volume made upto 50 ml for zinc and cadmium; for palladium instead of 0.5 g of KBr, 0.5 g of KI was taken). The precipitate was dried at <100°C for zinc and cadmium and at <110°C for palladium and weighed as $Cd(C_9H_7N)_2Br_2$, $Zn(C_9H_7N)_2Br_2$ and $Pd(C_9H_7N)_2I_2$ respectively. 4.22-42.17 mg of cadmium, 4.91-49.05 mg of zinc and 1.60-15.96 mg of palladium were determined with average error not more than $\pm 0.5\%$ in any case.

Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} do not interfere in the determination of Zn and Cd. thus giving a much higher tolerance than pyridine thiocyanate⁵, *o*-phenanthroline thiocyanate⁶ and 2-2'-dipyridyl thiocyanate⁷ methods. In case of palladium Pt^{2+} , Rh^{3+} , Ru^{3+} , $Os(IV)$ Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} do not interfere.

TABLE 1. SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF Cd-Co, Cd-Cu AND Cd-Ni
10 ml of 0.2M KBr = 10 ml of 0.2M KSCN = 20 ml of $Hg(NO_3)_2$

Amount of cadmium taken, mg	Amount of metal taken, mg	Volume of 0.2M KBr used by cadmium, ml	Volume of 0.2M KSCN used by Cd+M, ml	Volume of 0.2M KSCN used by metal, ml	Cadmium found, mg	Metal found, mg	% error	
							Cd	Metal
<i>Determination of Cd-Co</i>								
2.81	2.95	0.25	0.75	0.50	2.81	2.95	0.00	0.00
25.27	5.90	2.25	3.25	1.00	25.29	5.89	+0.04	-0.2
19.65	11.80	1.75	3.75	2.00	19.67	11.79	+0.10	-0.09
5.62	14.75	0.50	3.00	2.50	5.62	14.74	0.00	-0.08
<i>Determination of Cd-Cu</i>								
5.62	1.59	0.50	0.75	0.25	5.62	1.59	0.00	0.00
28.08	3.18	2.50	3.00	0.50	28.10	3.18	0.00	0.00
16.85	6.36	1.50	2.50	1.00	16.86	6.35	-0.06	-0.16
22.46	9.53	2.00	3.50	1.50	22.48	9.53	+0.09	0.00
<i>Determination of Cd-Ni</i>								
28.08	2.94	2.50	3.00	0.50	28.10	2.93	+0.06	-0.30
8.42	8.81	0.75	2.25	1.50	8.43	8.80	+0.12	-0.11
11.23	11.74	1.00	3.00	2.00	11.24	11.74	+0.09	0.00
2.81	14.68	0.25	2.75	2.50	2.81	14.67	0.00	-0.07

TABLE 2. SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF Zn-Co, Zn-Cu AND Zn-Ni
10 ml of 0.2M KBr = 10 ml of 0.2M KSCN = 20 ml of Hg(NO₃)₂

Amount of zinc taken, mg	Amount of metal taken, mg	Volume of 0.2M KBr used by zinc, ml	Volume of 0.2M KSCN used by Zn+M, ml	Volume of 0.2M KSCN used by metal, ml	Zinc found, mg	Metal found, mg.	% error	
							Zn	Metal
<i>Determination of Zn-Co</i>								
1.63	14.73	0.25	2.75	2.50	1.63	14.73	0.00	0.00
6.54	11.79	1.00	3.00	2.00	6.54	11.79	0.00	0.00
11.44	7.37	1.75	3.00	1.25	11.44	7.37	0.00	0.00
14.71	5.89	2.25	3.25	1.00	14.71	5.89	0.00	0.00
<i>Determination of Zn-Cu</i>								
19.61	1.59	3.00	3.25	0.25	19.61	1.59	0.00	0.00
13.07	6.35	2.00	3.00	1.00	13.07	6.35	0.00	0.00
8.17	9.53	1.25	2.75	1.50	8.17	9.53	0.00	0.00
4.90	13.71	0.75	2.75	2.00	4.90	13.71	0.00	0.00
<i>Determination of Zn-Ni</i>								
17.98	1.47	2.75	3.00	0.25	17.98	1.47	0.00	0.00
13.07	4.40	2.00	2.75	0.75	13.07	4.40	0.00	0.00
9.81	7.34	1.50	2.75	1.25	9.81	7.34	0.00	0.00
3.27	13.21	0.50	2.75	2.25	3.27	13.21	0.00	0.00

Volumetric determination of cadmium, zinc and palladium: To an aliquot of metal nitrate solution added isoquinoline solution and 10 ml. of 0.2M potassium bromide in case of cadmium and zinc, for palladium 10 ml of 0.1M potassium iodide was added. The proper pH were maintained. The volume was made upto 25 ml, allowed to stand for 10-15 min and filtered through Whatman no. 42 filter paper. The first few ml. of the filtrate were rejected, to 5 ml of the filtrate, added 10-15 ml of distilled water (adjusted the pH 3.0 in case of zinc and cadmium, in case of palladium there is no need of adjusting the pH but for better results instead of putting 10-15 ml of water, 10-15 ml of ethanol is to be added) 1-2 drops of the indicator and titrated with mercuric nitrate solution with the appearance of violet colour. The decrease in the concentration of bromide ions corresponded to zinc and cadmium while that of iodide ions corresponded to palladium. 2.81-22.48 mg of cadmium, 1.63-19.61 mg of zinc and 0.66-13.30 mg of palladium were determined with error not more than $\pm 0.01\%$ in any case.

Simultaneous determinations of Co-Cd, Cu-Cd, Ni-Cd, Co-Zn and Ni-Zn: These were found possible based upon the formation of isoquinoline halide and isoquinoline thiocyanate complexes. The results of these determinations are given in Tables 1 and 2.

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Role of Reactivity in Cupola Operation

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SINCE the carbon monoxide in stack gases of a cupola arise from the reaction of coke with carbon dioxide, according to the reaction $\text{CO}_2 + \text{C} \rightleftharpoons 2\text{CO}$, and also because different cokes have different reactivities towards carbon dioxide, it has often been assumed that the reactivity of coke towards carbon dioxide plays an important role in cupola operation.

Peter and coworkers^{1,2} have applied, to cupola operation, the principles of reaction kinetics of porous solids with gaseous substances. According to them, reaction in the combustion and lower part of the gasification zone, is controlled by boundary layer diffusion, in the top part of the gasification zone by pore diffusion, and in the preheating zone (the top part of the shaft) by chemical reaction. Since the gasification intensities in the chemical reaction region, are, by several magnitudes, smaller than those in the lower combustion and gasification regions, the former region is considered to be a relatively unimportant region, and for all practical purposes, it is

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